

MIGNEX Focus Group Data

This metadata sheet describes the MIGNEX Focus Group Data, which is available for research purposes, subject to approval.

Data type	Transcripts of focus group discussions
Unit of analysis	Focus groups
Geographical coverage	25 research areas across 10 countries in Africa, the Middle East and Asia (Cabo Verde, Guinea, Ghana, Nigeria, Ethiopia, Somalia, Tunisia, Turkey, Afghanistan, and Pakistan)
Timespan	Data collected between February 2020 and December 2021
Sample size	N = 646 participants across 104 focus group discussions
Population	General population aged 18–39
Data origin	Audio recorded discussions
Thematic coverage	Positive aspects about living in the research area; improvements or deteriorations during the last decade; potential paths towards livelihoods for young people in the area; attitudes towards migration in relation to the individual and the research area; livelihood recommendations.
Data file(s)	MIGNEX-Focus-Group-Descriptions.docx mignex-focus-group-data-2024-08-31.zip
Dataset citation	Please cite as displayed on the Zenodo page for this record.
Detailed documentation	Erdal, M.B. and Carling, J. (2020) Qualitative Data Collection, MIGNEX Handbook Chapter 8 (v1). Oslo: Peace Research Institute Oslo. Available at www.mignex.org/d041 . Erdal, M.B., Fitzmaurice, M., Ivanova, M., Hemat, L.E., Karl, E. (2023) Documentation of qualitative data collection, MIGNEX Handbook Chapter 11 (v2). Oslo: Peace Research Institute Oslo. Available at https://www.mignex.org/d042 . See also zenodo.org/communities/mignex for additional data and documentation and mignex.org for project information and publications.
Dataset managers	Marta Bivand Erdal (PRIO)